

D7.1 Project Handbook

101060184 – DiCE

Digital health in Circular Economy

WP7 – Project Management

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Document responsible	Els Ducheyne (JPNV)
Document editor	Jeroen Schuermans, Juliana Aizawa (Akkodis)
Other contributors	Conny Bakker (TUD), Rene Luigies (GSL)

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Document History

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V0.2	07/12/2022	Second draft for review to Consortium
V1.0	31/12/2022	Final version

History of Changes

Version	Chapter	Description

Definitions

- **Beneficiary or Partner.** Wording used in most of the legal documents. Legal entity who has signed the Grant Agreement with the European Research Executive Agency (REA) or the Form of Accession.
- **Consortium.** The DiCE Consortium, comprising the below-mentioned legal entities.
- **Consortium Agreement.** Agreement concluded amongst DiCE Beneficiaries for the implementation of the Grant Agreement.
- **Deliverable review.** An evaluation procedure by one or more reviewers, which precedes the distribution of a deliverable (as defined in the Work Plan) to the European Commission.
- **Grant Agreement.** The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the European Research Executive Agency (REA) for the undertaking of the DiCE project, with agreement nr.: 101060184.
- **Project.** The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement and its Annexes.
- **Work plan.** Schedule of tasks, deliverables, efforts, dates and responsibilities corresponding to the work to be carried out, as specified in Annex I to the Grant Agreement.
- **Risk.** Uncertainty that may have a significant impact on the execution or outcome of the project.

Abbreviations

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning
AB	Advisory Board
AGA	Annotated Model Grant Agreement
CA	Consortium Agreement
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
ExCom	Executive Committee
GA	General Assembly
LIPAC	Legal and IP Advisory Committee
PMO	Project Management Office
WP	Work Package

Beneficiaries of the DiCE Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

N°	Short Name	Role	Legal Name
1.	JPNV	CO	Janssen Pharmaceutica NV
1.1	J&J MD	AE	Johnson & Johnson Medical BV
1.2	JCBV	AE	Janssen-Cilag BV
2.	UGent	BEN	Universiteit Gent
3.	WEEE FORUM	BEN	Waste of Electrical and Electronic Equipment Forum AISBL
3.1	REC	AE	Recupel VZW
3.1	ECO	AE	Fundacion Ecolec
4.	LCL	BEN	Thomas More Kempen VZW
5.	TUD	BEN	Technische Universiteit Delft
6.	GSL	BEN	Game Solutions Lab BV
7.	GRIN	BEN	GRIN AS
8.	RUB	BEN	Ruhr-Universitaet Bochum
9.	PRE	BEN	Philips Electronics Nederland BV
10.	INTRAS	BEN	Fundacion Intras
11.	RDAPM	BEN	Regionalna razvojna agencija za Podravje - Maribor
12.	CBS	BEN	Copenhagen Business School
13.	EKOS	BEN	EKOSIJ DOO
14.	IETU	BEN	Instytut Ekologii Terenow Uprzemyslowionych
15.	MIREC	BEN	Mirec BV
16.	WRFA	AP	World Resources Forum Association
17.	ITU	BEN	IT-Universitetet I Kobenhavn

CO: Coordinator

AE: Affiliated Entity

BEN: Beneficiary

AP: Associated Partner

Introduction

This document is the central reference document related to different management procedures to be applied during the project lifetime of the DiCE project. All this content is largely defined in their legal terms in the Consortium Agreement signed by all DiCE partners. Summary guidelines are reported in this document for quicker operative consultation by the project partners. If, however, any discrepancy should exist between this document and the Grant Agreement or the Consortium Agreement or their annexes, the Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement and their annexes will take precedence. This document therefore starts with a summary of the project key data, a short description of the different consortium bodies and the organization of the different teams.

The project handbook also describes the project coordination and management, refers to key legal documents, describes the code of conduct and details the applicable procedures for reviewing deliverables and assuring quality thereof, periodic & financial reporting and risk management. It also provides guidelines for communication, both internal as well as external, dissemination, exploitation and Intellectual Property Rights. The document concludes by listing how the risks should be identified, assessed, and listed.

After submission of this document as a Deliverable, the DiCE project handbook will be maintained as a living document throughout the lifetime of the project, to be updated whenever necessary.

Within DiCE project, the main task of the Project Management Office (PMO), in collaboration with the Executive Committee, is to oversee and make sure that the project is running smoothly towards its objectives. Risk management is an important part of the work of the PMO: whenever you face a problem (e.g., change of legal status, change of staff and legal signatory, financial questions, delay in achieving a deliverable, etc.) you should inform the PMO immediately, as some decisions will have to be made, such as: amendments of the Grant Agreement and your administration for legal and financial issues, notification to the Horizon Europe Project Officer, discussion within the Consortium for deliverables, etc.

The PMO is here to help you!

Jeroen.schuermans@akkodisgroup.com

Juliana.abreu@akkodisgroup.com

educheyne@its.jnj.com

The general principles for the project execution are defined in the Grant Agreement, the Description of Action and in the Consortium Agreement provisions. This project handbook shall not replace any of the established agreements within the consortium. Where there are any apparent or real inconsistencies between these documents the following order of precedence shall be applied (see Section 4 of this document for further details on these documents):

1. Grant Agreement
2. Consortium Agreement
3. Project Handbook

1 Basic project information

Table 1 summarises the basic information of DiCE.

Table 1: DiCE Project Data

Project number	101060184
Project acronym	DiCE
Project name	Digital Health in a Circular Economy
Framework Programme	Horizon Europe
Call	HORIZON-CL6-2021-CIRCBIO-01
Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2021-CIRCBIO-01-04
Type of Action	Horizon Innovation Actions
Project Officers	Sotirios Kanellopoulos
Financial Officer	Daniela Tiralongo
Start date	October 1, 2022
Duration	48 months
Maximum grant amount	7,762,290.25 Euro
Person power	873.30 person months

2 Consortium members

Up to date contact information, including e-mail addresses and the work packages to which individuals are linked, can be found on the SharePoint of DiCE. Since this document is a public deliverable, e-mail addresses are not listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Consortium member data

Partner n°	Partner	Contact
1	JPNV	Els Ducheyne (Coordinator)
		Jason LaRoche
		Karl Jacobs
1.1 (AE)	J&JM	Marjolijn Klaver
1.2 (AE)	JCBV	Bert Hartog
2	UGENT	Lieselot Boone
		Naomi Ndunge Muindi
		Erasmus Cadena Martinez
		Jo Dewulf
3	WEEE Forum	James Horne
		Pascal Leroy
		Lucia Herreras
		Magdalena Charytanowicz
		Michelle Wagner
		Enikő Hajósi
		Maria Anta
Nanett Kalapos		
3.1 (AE)	Ecolec	Enrique Redondo Cascante
		Esperanza Hildago
		Luis Moreno
3.2 (AE)	Recupel	Eric Dewaet
		Lorenzo Glorie
4	LCL	Ingrid Adriaensen
		Nele De Witte
		Vicky Van der Auwera
5	TUD	Conny Bakker
		Tamara Hoveling
		Jeremy Faludi
6	GSL	Rob Tieben
		Suzanne Tholenaar
		Rene Luigies
7	GRIN	Daniel Millet
		Lars-Martin Berglund
		Jo Korneliussen
8	RUB	Christian Meske
		Hüseyin Keke

9	PRE	Michael Hessemans
		Hans Leijen
		Maikel van Niftrik
10	INTRAS	Rosa Almeida
		Raquel Losada Durán
		José Hernández Echegara
		Sofía Ballesteros Rodriguez
		Yoland Bueno
		Tere Cid-Bartolomé
11	RDAPM	Sabina Sneider
		Brina Novak
		Amna Potocnik
12	CBS	Christiane Lehrer
		Attila Márton
		Andreas Wieland
13	EKOSIJ	Borut Bernat
		Nastja Subic
14	IETU	Izabela Ratman-Kłosińska
15	MIREC	Alfred Jager
16 (AP)	WRFA	Shahrazad Manoochehri
		Sonia Valdivia
		Adrien Specker
		Salomé Stähli
		Mathias Schlupe
17	ITU	Daniel Fürstenau

AE: Affiliated Entity

AP: Associated Partner

3 Project coordination and management

3.1 Objectives

Within DiCE, WP7 Project Management aims at covering the operational project management activities by providing professional management to ensure satisfactory progress and successful completion. WP7 will also provide oversight and guidance of ethical aspects relevant to the project and strategic direction of the scientific and technical activities. To ensure that scientific activities are managed effectively this WP will also pay special attention to the integrated project plan, interdependencies and will draw special attention to cross-WP activities.

Its main objectives are as follows:

1. To ensure that the project is appropriately implemented according to the Grant Agreement and its project work plan, and that the general project activities are managed efficiently, with special attention to cross-WP activities, dependencies and budget assignments.
2. To manage resources, procedures and tools for ensuring that all expected results are delivered on time, with high quality level and within cost.
3. To establish standards and procedures for Quality Control.
4. To monitor designated milestones and deliverables for each work package to ensure compliance.
5. To establish management systems and procedures in the project, including risk management.
6. Monitoring risks and overseeing mitigation strategy.

The consortium bodies set up for DiCE include the persons, committees and other entities that are responsible for making management decisions, implementing management actions and their interrelation.

3.2 Management principles

The strategy followed for selecting the procedures described in this document is based on the following guiding principles:

1. **Adequacy** – Appropriateness for the general characteristics of the DiCE project and Consortium.
2. **Attainability** – Selected strategies must allow for implementation within a Consortium conformed by a variety of partners with different cultures, backgrounds, profiles, interests, levels of involvement, and degrees of expertise in management and quality issues. Since an active involvement of all Beneficiaries is needed, the last factor is regarded as most crucial. Therefore, a progressive approach that allows for increasing complexity and refinement of procedures over the project duration is to be favoured whenever possible.
3. **Efficiency** – The effort and resources spent in learning, implementing and maintaining the selected procedures cannot outweigh the benefits expected from their

effectiveness (understood as accuracy and completeness with which their goals are achieved). Selected strategies cannot create bottlenecks that hamper the timely delivery of committed results. While co-creation, compromised solutions and collaboration are founding principles of DiCE, which will facilitate reaching consensus, project decisions cannot be unjustifiably postponed when affecting the project's critical path and/or the Grant Agreement commitments.

4. **Flexibility** – Although suited for the project as a whole, strategies must allow for adaptation to changing needs derived from the project's own development, as well as changes in the environment.
5. **Reliability** – Strategies and procedures should be compliant with international standards, documented, and tested by past experience of partners and/or previous projects whenever possible.

3.3 Governance

The consortium structure of DiCE has been devised to respond to the needs of the project, its size and complexity. A brief overview on the governance structure is provided below (Figure 1 and Table 3).

Figure 1. Governance structure of DiCE

- The **General Assembly (GA)** is the decision-making body of the consortium as set out in Section 6.2 of the Consortium Agreement. The **Executive Committee (ExCom)** shall supervise project implementation and risk management. It is ultimately responsible for the determination of DiCE's policies and the overall scientific leadership of the project, ensuring alignment, scientific coherence and coordination across work packages. The Executive Committee is further defined in section 6.3 of the Consortium Agreement.
- Each **Work Package (WP)** Team is composed of members representing the partner organisation participating in the relevant WP. The WP leaders are in charge of ensuring that the work planned in their work package is carried out properly and on time. The Work Package Leaders are the interface between the different partners involved in

each WP and the Coordinator. Meeting frequency is at WP leaders' discretion and WP Leaders are in charge of organising and chairing WP meetings.

- The **Executive Committee (ExCom)** is responsible for the overall execution of the Project, alignment across all work packages, decision making and the initial finding of amicable solutions for any disputes between the Parties relating to the execution of the Project.
- The **Coordinator** is the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority. The Coordinator shall, in addition to its responsibilities as a Party, perform the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.
- The **Project Management Office (PMO)**, who will act as secretary to the General Assembly, Executive Committee, Legal and IP Advisory Committee, and Advisory Board is further defined in Section 6.5 of the Consortium Agreement.
- The **Legal and IP Advisory Committee (LIPAC)** will deal with all legal and IP related aspects of the Project as set out in Section 6.6 of this Consortium Agreement.
- The independent **Advisory Board (AB)** is an Advisory Board that will act as an independent third-party providing feedback and consisting of European and international organizations with extensive expertise in the circular economy field as set out in Section 6.7 of the Consortium Agreement.

Table 3: Consortium Bodies set up for DiCE governance

Consortium Bodies	Beneficiaries
General Assembly	Chair: Els Ducheyne (JPNV) One representative of each Party signing the Consortium Agreement
Executive Committee	Chair: Els Ducheyne (JPNV) All Work Package Leaders Representatives of the PMO
Coordinator	Els Ducheyne (JPNV)
Project Management Office	Els Ducheyne (JPNV) supported by Anca Florea, Jeroen Schuermans, Juliana Aizawa (Akkodis, contractor of JPNV)
Legal and IP Advisory Committee	Chair: Els Ducheyne (JPNV) Hans Leyen (PHI) Alfred Jager (MIREC) Rolling membership
Advisory Boards	See terms of reference for Advisory Board
Work Package Leaders	WP1: Magdalena Charytanowicz/James Horne (WEEE Forum) WP2: Conny Bakker (TU Delft) WP3: Daniel Millet (GRIN) WP4: Vicky Van der Auwera (LiCaLabs) WP5: Erasmo Cadena (UGent) WP6: Bert Hartog (JCBV) WP7: Els Ducheyne (JPNV)

For detailed description, voting rights and tasks of the committees, please refer to the DoA, and Section 6 of the Consortium Agreement.

3.4 Project Meetings

The Coordinator, supported by the PMO, shall in accordance with the Consortium Agreement, convene meetings of the governance bodies at the DiCE overall level (i.e. GA and ExCom), complying with the frequency of ordinary meetings as defined in the DiCE Consortium Agreement. WP leads hold the responsibility of calling meetings within their respective WPs as needed.

According to the Consortium Agreement, the bodies of the DiCE governance will have the following approximate meeting frequency (see Table 4):

- GA is to be held at least once per year, and ad hoc if required
- ExCom meetings are organized at minimum once per quarter
- WP meetings as needed
- LIPAC is only called when required
- AB are convened at the General Assembly meeting

Table 4. Meeting schedule for one working year of DiCE

	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
GA	1					1						
ExCom	1											
WP	1											
LIPAC	Ad hoc											
AB	1											

3.4.1 DiCE Face-to-Face General Assembly meeting organisation

All DiCE partners may volunteer to host DiCE General Assembly meetings and other meetings related to the project. The hosting partner and the PMO will share the responsibility of the meeting organisation. The list of host roles and responsibilities below is indicative and intended to help identify the commitments at both sides and may vary slightly for each specific meeting:

Host responsibilities

- Before the meeting:
 - Identification, initial visits and initial negotiation with meeting venues (ideally 2-3 options). Venue requirements:
 - Reasonable cost (range to be confirmed) via a daily delegate rate
 - Flexibility to implement a delegate rate, if applicable
 - Availability of plenary room, plus smaller break-out rooms
 - Catering service
 - Audio-visual equipment / Teleconference (TC) equipment

- Identification, initial visits and negotiation with hotel (ideally the same as the meeting venue). Negotiation of special rate if possible. Pre-blocking of rooms if possible.
- Identification, initial visits and negotiation with restaurant for one project dinner (for practical reasons, it is recommended to have it in the same place as the venue or in the proximity of the meeting venue.
- Join the organisation team during one on-site visit, if required
- Support the organisation team in dealing with incidences that require on-site interventions
- Participate in meeting organisation teleconferences (TCs) as needed
- Facilitate contact with provider to print the meeting material, if required
- During the meeting:
 - Provide support during the meeting (e.g. for registration desk, audio-visual equipment and TC facilities tests, etc.)
- After the meeting:
 - Financial follow-up related to the venue and restaurant if relevant and/or required

3.4.2 Face-to-Face meeting participation

Each DiCE partner should book their travel, accommodation and pay her/his dinner costs and delegate rate (if applicable), which should be covered by themselves from their own project travel budget and then claimed directly to the EU at the time of their organisation's periodic financial reporting (if eligible to receive EU funding). The process on how to claim the travel costs can be found in section 6.4 of this handbook.

3.5 Main responsibilities of DiCE partners

Partners must endeavor to perform and fulfil, promptly, and on time, all of their obligations under the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement, to accomplish the purpose and objectives of the DiCE project and act in cooperation and mutual trust. Partners shall also provide their respective contributions to deliverables, information, and reports as required by the WP leads, the GA, the ExCom, the PMO, and the Coordinator, so as to help these bodies to fulfil their obligations.

Partners shall promptly notify the Coordinator and the PMO through the appropriate WP lead of any significant problem or delay likely to affect the success of the project.

In summary, each Beneficiary must:

- Do the work they have been assigned to in the Description of Action, and any other detailed work plan derived from it, on time and with an appropriate level of quality. Deliverables should be finalised with the ultimate goal of future exploitation of the project results in mind.
- Collaborate with all other partners as required by the tasks, including contributing to relevant deliverables.

- Not hinder the work of others or delay it unnecessarily.
- Attend meetings and teleconferences as required.
- Notify promptly the relevant governance body of any potential issue affecting performance. The normal chain of reporting would be, in this order: WP Lead -> PMO + Coordinator -> ExCom -> GA.
- Notify the PMO + Coordinator and ExCom about any risk that may be detected in the course of the work, and that may affect future performance.
- Fulfil the administrative, technical, and financial reporting obligations according to EU rules – spend the costs foreseen only for the work expected in DiCE and report it faithfully.

3.6 Resolving internal conflicts

In the event that an internal conflict arises at a given time, the project management structure is formulated to support a bottom-up approach with respect to its resolution.

Conflicts amongst partners in any given activity will be discussed at the WP level with the help of the respective WP Leaders.

4 Key legal documents

4.1 Grant Agreement

The Grant Agreement is the main legal document underpinning the project's execution effectively, a contract between the Beneficiaries and the European Commission (EC). It is first signed by the EC and the Coordinator. Each DiCE beneficiary then accedes to the Grant Agreement by signing an accession form. The Grant Agreement mainly provides information on the grant (parties, duration, start date, budget, maximum funding, etc.), obligations of the beneficiaries towards the EC (such as reporting requirements), as well as the intellectual property framework and other legal conditions. The Grant Agreement is dated 07/06/2022 and has the number 101060184.

The following chapters are included in the Grant Agreement:

- Chapter 1 - General: an introductory chapter regarding the subject of the agreement and the major definitions.
- Chapter 2 – Action: Duration and starting dates
- Chapter 3 – Grant: Everything about the grant (form, maximum amounts, budget flexibility), as well as eligible and ineligible costs and contribution are included here.
- Chapter 4 – Grant Implementation. This chapter is split into three sections
 - Section 4.1 – Beneficiaries, affiliated entities and other participants. This subsection is defining the actual consortiums, going into specific details if needed (e.g. participants with special status such as Non-EU ones or international organizations)
 - Section 4.2 – Rules to carry out the action. This covers topics from confidentiality and security, data protection, ethics and values to conflict of

- interests and intellectual property rights (IPR). It also include visibility (communication and dissemination and specific rules (if any))
- Section 4.3 – Administration. This sub-section includes general information obligations and issues like reporting (reporting language, periodic reports, consequences of non-compliance etc.), guarantees, certificates, payments and recoveries, impact evaluations and checks, reviews and audits.
- Chapter 5 – Consequences of Non-compliance. It consists of four sections.
 - Section 5.1 – Rejection and Grant reduction. A description of conditions, procedures and effects.
 - Section 5.2 – Suspension and Termination. On top of relevant conditions and procedures, this sub-section also includes the processes for Grant Agreement suspension and/or termination initiated either from EU or from the beneficiaries.
 - Section 5.3 – Other consequences. These could be damages (liability of the granting authority or the beneficiaries) or administrative sanctions and other measures.
 - Section 5.4 – Force Majeure.
- Chapter 6 – Final Provisions.

Beyond its core terms and conditions, mostly standard text, the Grant Agreement also includes the following annexes, which form an integral part of the contract:

- Annex I. Description of the action
- Annex II. Estimated budget for the action
- Annex IIa. Additional information on unit costs and contributions
- Annex III. Accession form for beneficiaries
- Annex IIIa. Declaration of joint and several liability of Affiliated Entities
- Annex IV. Model for the financial statements
- Annex V. Specific rules (if applicable)

The most extensive and important Annex to the Grant Agreement is the Description of Action (DoA), which comprises the technical description of the work to be undertaken in the project (work packages, tasks, deliverables, milestones), the description and roles of the different partners, allocated efforts in person-months, and budget details. The DoA is derived from the original proposal submitted to the EC for evaluation and approval, and it is the benchmark against which project progress will be judged. Compared to the rest of the Grant Agreement and Annexes, which are mostly model texts, the DoA is specific to each project. It is important to remember that the DoA is an integral part of the Grant Agreement, and therefore it is a contractual commitment from all Beneficiaries.

To help users understand and interpret the Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement and provide answers to common issues and questions, the European Commission also published in November 2021 the so-called [Annotated Model Grant Agreement](#) (AGA), which explains the details of the General MGA (Model Grant Agreement).

4.2 Amendments to the Grant Agreement

The Grant Agreement can and must be changed whenever any important project parameter changes: Consortium composition, project duration, project budget and allocation, etc. Implementation of such changes must follow a specific procedure called ‘Grant Agreement Amendment’. Most changes that trigger Grant Agreement Amendments relate to updates in the DoA (e.g., changes in tasks and deliverables, changes in efforts allocated, additional partners, certain budget transfers across Beneficiaries, etc.). These can be relatively minor, in which case they tend to be grouped and implemented together in one go, or major, which might trigger an amendment on their own, especially if it is urgent that the change is officially entered into the contract.

Grant Agreement amendments are submitted to the EC by the Coordinator on behalf of the Consortium. This implies that the Consortium must be aware of and approve any proposed changes before the amendment is requested.

The PMO will be responsible for following-up on amendments to the Grant Agreement during the project. Partners need to contact the PMO + Coordinator if updates are identified for inclusion on the DoA. The PMO will also communicate the contents of these changes to the Executive Committee.

The overall procedure for amending the Grant Agreement is described in Article 39.2 of the Grant Agreement. In addition, the internal procedure required prior to the submission of the Amendment request is as follows:

1. The PMO will keep track of all needed amendments requested by the beneficiaries/partners. Meetings and communications with the Beneficiaries affected will enable to compile all the necessary information to support the changes. The PMO will also liaise with the ExCom on this tracking.
2. The PMO will circulate a list of requested changes to the Executive Committee for validation and information approval.
3. The PMO will prepare the following documentation:
 - a. A new version of the DoA with the modifications in track changes.
 - b. A first version of a “Amendment Request Letter” to be sent to the EC, including the changes and their rationale.
 - c. Other documents needed to request the modifications.
4. The ExCom will receive a copy of the prepared documentation and proceed with a final review. After agreement, the LIPAC shall coordinate any amendments to the Consortium Agreement.
5. The approval by the General Assembly will be required for any Amendment to the Grant Agreement, as defined in the Grant Agreement article 39.2 (Amendments to the Grant Agreement – Procedure), in accordance with Clause 6.2.7 of the Consortium Agreement.
6. As a final step, the Coordinator supported by the PMO will submit, on behalf of the Consortium, the Amendment Request Letter, the new version of the DoA and all the additional documentation required by the EC for the changes submitted. The new

version of the DoA will also be accessible in the DiCE document sharing platform (SharePoint).

4.3 Consortium agreement

The Consortium Agreement (CA) is concluded between the Beneficiaries aiming to provide a legal framework for their collaboration within the boundaries of the Grant Agreement. The CA includes provisions on governance, intellectual property, dissemination, and liability among others. The European Commission is not a party to the CA. The signed version of the CA is accessible on the DiCE document sharing platform (SharePoint).

Amendments to the CA may also be necessary during the project, sometimes purely because of Grant Agreement amendments. These CA amendments will be handled separately by agreement of all Beneficiaries, under the coordination of the Coordinator, with the support of the PMO.

5 Deliverables and quality control

5.1 Quality policy

High quality standards are to be applied to all work undertaken throughout the project. Quality and its pursuit are regarded as important for every individual activity within the project. Criteria and standards by which the quality of both the results of the project and the processes involved in their production are detailed below.

5.2 Quality control

The overall quality control of the project results includes the coordination of quality review for deliverables, prior to their submission to the EC.

It is crucial for the project to ensure that deliverables, as official results of the project, are reviewed and checked for quality. This may also apply to other outcomes of the project that are addressed to parties external to the project.

The present document focuses only on the general methods implemented to ensure quality of written materials delivered to the EC and other partners external to the Consortium. A document produced in a project generally aims to provide information concerning the work, its progress or the derived results. Each document should be carefully drafted with rich content, a clear structure and a professional presentation.

In DiCE, the three basic aspects for building quality into project documents are content, appearance and timing. It is generally accepted that the relative importance of each document varies, and it is important that over-zealous quality criteria do not compromise timing for marginal benefit to the project.

5.3 Generation of Deliverables

As official results of the project, Deliverables deserve special attention and are generated and reviewed according to specific procedures (see Section 5.4 and 9.2.3). As a general rule, the generation of Deliverables is the responsibility of the corresponding Lead Beneficiary as set out in the DoA, who need to gather contributions from Beneficiaries as appropriate. Prior to submission to the EC, Deliverables will undergo an internal review process that is detailed hereunder.

In order to ensure homogeneity in the presentation and facilitate consolidation of contributions from different partners, a template for reports and Deliverables has been generated, and is available through the SharePoint document repository.

The authors of a Deliverable/WP Lead have to indicate whether the Deliverable is for public or private (Consortium-restricted) use to ensure correct confidentiality handling in accordance with the provisions of the Consortium Agreement. Whether a Deliverable is confidential, or public is indicated specifically for each deliverable separately in the DoA under its dissemination level. This will be also outlined in the deliverable template (latest version available on SharePoint).

All Deliverables must be developed in the language of the Grant Agreement, i.e., English.

With regards to naming convention for electronic files, it is strongly recommended to use a reference that allows an easy and rapid understanding.

Example: ACRONYM_Del#_Title_Version#.

(e.g. DiCE_D7.1_Project Handbook_v1.0.pdf)

5.4 Review procedure

5.4.1 Quality criteria

The review process uses the following quality criteria as reference.

Regarding content:

- **Completeness:** Information must address all aspects related to the purpose of the information. The deliverable should be complete and in line with the original specifications of the project and thus should fulfil the required criteria outlined in the DoA. On the other hand, redundancy of information must be avoided, as it obscures the clarity of documents.

Related indicators: Missing content, Redundancy.

- **Methodological Accuracy and data integrity:** Information contained in the document must be reliable and verifiable. This means that all background information used in the reports should be appropriately supported by references. Information on results should be sufficiently supported so that misinterpretation is avoided. Use of statistically validated objective data is to be prioritised. Adherence to methodological accuracy is required.

Related indicators: Error, Insufficient references/objective supporting data, Ambiguity.

- **Accuracy on logic/writing/depth:** All information used, should be provided to the depth needed for the purpose of the document.

Related indicators: Lacking detail, Excessive detail.

- **Relevance:** Information used in the document should be focused on the key issues and be written in a manner that takes into consideration the target audience.

Related indicators: Irrelevant information.

As regards to appearance and structure:

- **Adherence to standards:** it is important that documents are prepared with uniform appearance and structure so that, even if they are produced by different authors, they appear as originating from a single initiative (see Deliverables Template).

Related indicators: Lack of uniformity in presentation.

- **WP leads:** Before submitting the first draft for review, it is recommended to align content and completeness on WP-level with the WP Leads, to make sure that there are no constraints regarding confidentiality, incomplete or unsuitable content.

Related indicators: Alignment on content and suitability on WP level.

5.4.2 Deliverable review process

Deliverables will follow the same review procedure as described in Section 9.2.3 of this Project Handbook. In addition to this process, for each deliverable, 2 dedicated reviewers will be identified. Depending on the subject, reviewers may be either members of the WP that are not involved in the generation of the deliverable or members of other WPs. Ideally, the 2 reviewers should not have been involved in the production of the deliverable and should represent different backgrounds, e.g., academic, public, industry.

Reviewers will be asked to check the deliverable against the quality criteria described above and submit their comments by using the “track changes” and “comment” tools of the document editor. The principal author(s) must proceed with the amendments and provide the PMO and reviewers with either a revised deliverable, specifying the corrective actions undertaken (in track changes), or with comments on the reviewed document justifying how each major feedback point has been addressed.

The final version of the document is then produced by the Author(s) and submitted to the PMO, who distributes it to the GA for awareness. The PMO submits the final document to the EC via the Partner Portal online tool. The final document will be published on the project SharePoint.

During the entire process, it is recommended that there is one responsible author who acts on behalf of all authors and coordinates the development of the document.

5.5 Delays of Deliverables and Milestones

The due dates of all DiCE deliverables are listed in the DoA and in the EU Portal. In case a Deliverable or Milestone is delayed, the WP lead must notify to the PMO and ExCom without any delay. This notification must include a justification of the delay, including an analysis of the impact to the DiCE project. In parallel, the risk assessment and mitigation plan need to be performed. If the delay is approved by the ExCom, then the PMO informs the EC.

6 Reporting

This section describes the different reporting processes required during project execution. An overview of the different levels of reporting is provided in Table 5 below.

Table 5. Overview of the reporting processes

Reporting processes	Short description
Continuous reporting	Submission of Deliverables, updates of milestones and risks, etc in the EU portal. This process is coordinated by the Coordinator and the PMO with the help of all Beneficiaries.
Periodic reporting	Technical and financial reporting at the end of each review period. Approval of Periodic Reporting will trigger the payments from the EU to the Coordinator. This process is coordinated by the Coordinator and the PMO. The technical report is driven by the Coordinator and the PMO. Financial reporting is the responsibility of all Beneficiaries.
Interim reporting	Internal progress reporting by the WP leads to the ExCom to monitoring and reviewing the project's progress.

6.1 Continuous reporting

DiCE must continuously report on the progress of the action (e.g., deliverables, milestones, outputs/outcomes, critical risks, indicators, etc; if any), in the Portal Continuous Reporting tool and in accordance with the timing and conditions it sets out (as agreed with the granting authority).

Standardised deliverables (e.g., progress reports not linked to payments, reports on cumulative expenditure, special reports, etc; if any) must be submitted using the templates published on the Portal.

The continuous reporting process will be coordinated by the Coordinator, in support of the PMO. The progress report will be prepared with the input of the WP leads and all partners. WP Leads will collect the information from partners, add their contributions to the WP report, complete the deliverables, milestones and risk tables and check all information specific to the WP. All partners will describe the progress achieved in the tasks involved, the results obtained, any deviation from the DoA.

All reporting must be in the language of the Grant Agreement, i.e., English.

6.2 Periodic reporting: technical and financial reporting

DiCE must provide reports to request payments, in accordance with the schedule and modalities set out in the Grant Agreement Data Sheet (Table 6).

The prefinancing and periodic reports include a technical and financial part. The technical part includes an overview of the action implementation. It must be prepared using the template available in the Portal Periodic Reporting tool. The financial part of the additional prefinancing report includes a statement on the use of the previous prefinancing payment. The financial part of the periodic report includes:

- The financial statements (individual and consolidated; for all beneficiaries/affiliated entities)
- The explanation on the use of resources (or detailed cost reporting table, if required)
- The [Certificates on the Financial Statements](#) (CFS) (if required)

Table 6. DiCE Periodic Reporting

Reporting					Payments	
Reporting periods			Type	Deadline	Type	Deadline
RP n°	Start	End				
					Initial prefinancing	30 days from entry into force
1	1	18	Periodic report	60 days after end of reporting period	Interim payment	90 days from receiving periodic report
2	19	36	Periodic report	60 days after end of reporting period	Interim payment	90 days from receiving periodic report
3	37	48	Periodic report	60 days after end of reporting period	Final payment	90 days from receiving periodic report

6.3 Internal interim reporting and monitoring

Considering that formal reporting to EC occurs in month 18, 36 and at project end, and with the aim of monitoring and reviewing the project's progress, an internal progress report will be required from Beneficiaries every 6 months.

This report will include summarised information on the main achievements and work developed in each WP per participant, but also an estimation of the total effort spent in that period, expressed in person months and, possibly, total costs incurred per Beneficiary (an example of Interim Report template can be found in Annex I). This will allow analysing deviations vs the budget expected for that period. For it to be effective, the interim report should be as informative as possible and at the same time does not represent an excessive overhead for Beneficiaries, so that actionable data is gathered in a timely fashion. For this reason, the format and content of the interim report will be adjusted as needed over the project lifetime.

The information for the interim report will be submitted to the PMO who will consolidate it into a single report and use it to provide recommendations for corrective action to the ExCom. The information gathered through the above-mentioned internal reports will help the Coordinator in preparing the overview of the work done in the corresponding periodic report and the review meetings with the EC, but mostly it will be used to monitor the project's progress, detect resource under- and over-spending, and trigger early warnings and correction mechanisms as appropriate.

6.4 Financial reporting

6.4.1 Basic principles

The DiCE estimated budget is set out in Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement. It contains the estimated eligible costs and contributions for the action, broken down by Beneficiary and budget category. Annex 2 also shows the types of costs and contributions (forms of funding) to be used for each budget category. If unit costs or contributions are used, the details on the calculation will be explained in Annex 2a.

The funding rate for costs is 100% of the eligible costs for beneficiaries that are non-profit legal entities and 70% of the eligible costs for beneficiaries that are profit legal entities.

More information and details on the budget categories are available in Article 6 of the [AGA](#).

6.4.2 Eligibility and ineligibility

In order to be eligible, costs and contributions must meet the eligibility conditions set out in Article 6 of the Grant Agreement:

- Article 6.1: General eligibility conditions
- Article 6.2: Specific eligibility conditions for each budget category
- Article 6.3: Ineligible costs and contributions

6.4.3 Financial statements

The financial statements must detail the eligible costs and contributions for each budget category and, for the final payment, also the revenues for the action (see Articles 6 and 22 of the Grant Agreement).

All eligible costs and contributions incurred should be declared, even if they exceed the amounts indicated in the estimated budget (see Grant Agreement Annex 2). Amounts that are not declared in the individual financial statements will not be taken into account by the granting authority.

Beneficiaries will have to submit also the financial statements of their affiliated entities (if any). In case of recoveries (see Article 22 of the Grant Agreement), beneficiaries will be held responsible also for the financial statements of their affiliated entities.

6.4.4 Certificate on Financial Statements (CFS)

All beneficiaries with a requested EU contribution exceeding €430.000, must provide certificates on their financial statements (CFS). (Special threshold for beneficiaries with a

systems and process audit (see Article 24 of the Grant Agreement): financial statement: requested EU contribution to costs \geq €725 000).

The Coordinator must submit the CFS as part of the periodic report. The certificates must be drawn up using the [template](#) published on the EU Portal, cover the costs declared on the basis of actual costs and costs according to usual cost accounting practices (if any). For additional information and conditions, see section 24.2 of the Grant Agreement.

Partners required to submit a CFS are:

1-JPNV	2-UGent	3-WEEE Forum	4-LCL
5-TUD	7-GRIN	9-PRE	17-ITU

6.4.5 Adjustments to financial reporting

Any adjustment (retroactive modification of costs submitted in previous periods) requires the submission of a supplementary Financial Statement for the period, where the details of that adjustment will appear. Together with the new Financial Statement, the details and justification for the adjustment must be provided by the Beneficiary in the periodic report.

Therefore, for correction of financial statements submitted in previous reporting periods, the following needs to be submitted:

1. One Financial statement for the current period;
2. One separate Financial Statement for every previous period where adjustments are needed, which will include those adjusted (negative/positive) costs of that specific previous period.

If these costs need to be covered by a CFS, they could be supported within the CFS for the current period but with a specific indication by the auditor certifying both the supplementary costs incurred in previous periods and those claimed in the current one.

7 Risk management

Risks are inherent in any activity, especially when the activities differ a lot and are unique as in the case of this project. The presence of risk increases dramatically when projects include a significant research component, due to its inherently exploratory nature and uncertain outcome. The inevitability of risks does not imply however the inability to recognise and manage risks in order to minimise the potential negative consequences while taking advantage of the opportunities for improving performance and results that may arise. Risk management in the DiCE project is the process that commences with the identification of risks and links this to the resolution of individual risks. It encompasses the methods and procedures undertaken by the Consortium in order to identify, analyse, assess and monitor risks affecting the project or its results, and the development and monitoring of associated mitigation and contingency plans that aim at minimising the potential negative effects (for threat risks) and maximising the potential benefits (for opportunity risks).

The activity of Risk Management is depicted in Task 7.3 of the DoA.

7.1 Risk Management objectives

The fundamental goal of risk management is to maximize the chances of project success and thereby efficient use of the resources allocated to the project.

The main objectives of the DiCE risk management task to reach this goal, are the following:

1. To consult with the WP-Leads and ExCom on potential areas of risk and possible mitigation strategies ahead of any possible occurrence, and regularly update these working closely with the WP-leaders;
2. To provide visibility and raise awareness of uncertainties that may affect the project development and/or results through a structured mechanism that ensures that both completeness and accuracy will be achieved in the process;
3. To allow the project to focus on major risks by appropriate assessment and prioritisation according to risk exposure, a value that results of combining the estimated probability and impact values for any given risk;
4. To proactively manage uncertainties that can affect the project performance, time schedule and/or budget, with proper feedback channels to project management, allowing for the development of contingency plans, mitigation and/or risk avoidance strategies.
5. To continuously monitor the evolution of risks throughout the project, providing a framework to incorporate them in the work plan (as risks become issues) or disregard them (risks becoming pure concerns);
6. To document risks, activities and decisions made so as to allow for capitalisation of the knowledge acquired with a view on facilitating planning and development of the post-project phase and future projects.

7.2 Risk Management procedures

The risk management procedures in DiCE have been adapted from lessons learnt in past projects by the Consortium, from guidelines produced by international standards bodies, and by recognised institutions such as the PMI.

The Coordinator, in support of the PMO, is responsible for risk management procedures within the project and facilitates straight forward and timely communication with the ExCom. However, risk management activities certainly benefit from the active participation of all involved actors, therefore an open structure that allows for contributions from all project partners is promoted. Namely, the WP will be involved actively to identify possible risks.

An overview of the 4 main steps of the risk management process is detailed below (**Error! Reference source not found.**):

1. Risk identification
2. Risk assessment
3. Risk registry and action plan
4. Risk monitoring

An overview of the main actions to take when identifying a risk is provided in Section 7.3.

Figure 2. Overview of the Risk Management process.

7.2.1 Risk identification

Before risks can be managed, they must be identified. Identification raises awareness of risks before they become problems and adversely affect the project. The first phase of the risk management process deals with systematic research for threats to the successful achievement of the project objectives, or for opportunities that may be hidden therein, and their appropriate classification. This process relies heavily on the encouragement of Work Package Leads and contributors to raise concerns and issues for subsequent analysis, as past experience has demonstrated that most risks are usually known by the personnel, who usually experience them as uneasy feelings, concerns or doubts about aspects of the project that wouldn't be defined as risks per se and thus remain hidden. The Risk Identification process must create and sustain a non-judgmental and non-attributive risk elicitation environment so that tentative or controversial views are not discouraged.

The outcome of the risk identification process will be the creation of a **Risk Documentation Form** (see template provided in Annex II) for each identified risk. A **Risk Registry** composed of the regularly updated Risk Documentation Forms will be maintained by the PMO.

Both opportunity and threat risks will be identified in the same way.

7.2.2 Risk assessment

An initial risk assessment is normally carried out as a natural consequence of the identification process. With the help of risk assessment, risk data can be turned into risk decision-making information, and provides the basis for the Project Managers to work on the "right" risks. It aims at estimating the likelihood (probability) of a risk becoming a problem, the estimated impact ("damage" or "severity" in relation to the project objectives fulfilment) and an associated risk exposure, which is a consequence of the two former variables. In DiCE, a qualitative method will be initially used for estimation, ranking both probability and impact on a three-point scale (high, medium or low). In this simple scheme, risks having at least one dimension graded as "high" are always to be closely examined. However, quantification of the risk exposure is done by multiplying the numerical values ascribed to each grade in the scale as follows:

	Impact	Low	Medium	High
Probability	Values	1	2	3
Low	1	1	2	3
Medium	2	2	4	6
High	3	3	6	9

A simple three-level scale will be applied, as more complex scales have proven to produce biases in the prioritisation in past projects. If needed and by the decision of the ExCom, the method can be refined according to an alternative method to allow for more precise prioritisation of the top ranked risks¹.

It is important to take into account that interaction and inter-dependence between risks can occur, and that in some cases these complex situations should be treated as independent risks in themselves.

Risk assessment encompasses a prioritisation of the risks that can be made according to exposure, but that can also be filtered according to risk category or imminence in time. This phase also comprises a specification of the Risk owner, understood as the partner in the best position to recommend mitigation strategies for the risk, develop and document a contingency plan and monitor the status of the risk. This normally corresponds to the partner responsible of the activity or WP to which the risk is ascribed. The partner who is the Risk owner is responsible of closely following up the risk and report to the Coordinator and the PMO, if necessary.

7.2.3 Risk registry and action plan

On the basis of the previous assessment, the planning phase turns risk information into decisions and actions (both present and future) to address individual risks. This phase comprises:

- The **definition of mitigation approaches** - strategies to control, avoid, minimise or otherwise mitigate the risk, addressed to reduce risk probability and/or impact for threat risks, and the opposite for opportunity risks;
- **Identification of trigger events** - conditions that indicate that the risk is turning into an issue;
- **Configuration of contingency plans** - actions to be taken to deal with the situation if the risk actually becomes a problem.

All threat risks with "high" or "medium" probability or impact should have a mitigation strategy that must be immediately tackled and all risks having an exposure equal or greater

¹ The alternative method defines *probability* on a scale ranging from 0.1 (highly improbable) to 1.0 (certain to happen), while *impact* is defined on a scale from 1 (extremely reduced impact) to 10 (huge impact), in which case prioritisation will be derived from the risk exposure factor (result of multiplying the probability and impact factors).

than 4 must have a contingency plan prepared in DiCE. Additionally, a mitigation plan is required to be produced for all risks that can be easily mitigated, or that the PMO wishes to mitigate for strategic reasons. A mitigation strategy contains a plan for controlling either or both of the following:

- The risk cause/cause-impact relationship with the aim to reduce the impact probability of occurrence.
- The impact itself and/or its effect on the project.

Implementation of a mitigation approach is a responsibility of the Risk Owner, who will be supported by the Coordinator and the PMO, especially when other partners are involved.

Contingency plans should identify the proposed management activity or alternative path to be taken in case that the risk gives clear indications (understood as occurrence of trigger events) that it cannot be avoided. Contingency plan implementation are Project Management issues and often have to be agreed in DiCE with the EC to be entered into the Work Plan. Contingency plans and responsibilities for their implementation are agreed upon at ExCom level.

In summary, mitigation actions are what one does before the risk happens; once trigger events are detected, the risk becomes an issue and contingency plans are activated. If mitigation is successful, trigger events are de-activated and the risk is managed out, or becomes irrelevant.

In all cases, risk **avoidance strategies** (which normally imply taking a lower risk path) have to be carefully considered, provided that they do not endanger the Grant Agreement fulfilment.

7.2.4 Risk monitoring

Risks and related actions undertaken must be monitored and re-assessed continuously throughout the project until they are managed out. Previously identified risks with mitigation strategies and contingency plans need to be closely tracked to ensure that any consequential or residual risks are identified as early as possible, and that actions decided are duly carried out.

The Coordinator, supported by the PMO, coordinates the re-assessment of risks if necessary and promoting the early identification and documentation of new risks.

The Risk Owner, supported by the Coordinator and the PMO, is responsible for maintaining the Risk Documentation Forms, following up on risks. The Coordinator and the PMO will support Risk Owners in the carrying out of mitigation actions that involve other partners as well.

WP Leads or an assigned Project Manager on WP-level will be responsible to monitor the risks more closely on WP-level.

The PMO is also responsible for organising internal risk review meetings if required to track top risks, and for documenting the whole risk management process, including mitigation and

implemented contingency plans and their results. Communication will be maintained with all partners and proactive participation and visibility of current risks will be promoted, using SharePoint. Risk reviews will be held during ExCom meetings to have a basis to decide on contingency plans to be executed. The PMO is responsible for checking the EC services about the appropriateness of any contingency plans that have the potential to endanger the work plan fulfilment and the successful completion of the project. The PMO is also responsible for updating the risk in the continuous reporting module of the EU Portal.

7.3 Risk management Actions (overview)

Action	Responsibility	Tasks
Risk management	Coordinator with PMO support	Straight forward and timely communication with the ExCom
Risk identification	All partners	WP leads and contributors to raise concerns and issues
Risk documentation form	Risk owner, supported by the Coordinator and the PMO	For each identified risk, documentation is created
Risk registry	PMO	A registry of the regularly updated Risk Documentation Forms will be maintained
Risk assessment	Risk owner	Closely following up the risk and report to the Coordinator and the PMO, if necessary
Risk mitigation	Risk owner, supported by the Coordinator and the PMO	Definition of mitigation approaches, identification of trigger events and configuration of contingency plans
Contingency plan approval	ExCom	Approve the actions to be taken to deal with the situation if the risk becomes a issue
Risk monitoring	WP Leads or an assigned Project Manager on WP-level will be responsible to monitor the risks more closely on WP-level	Risks and related actions undertaken must be monitored and re-assessed continuously throughout the project until they are managed out
Risk review	ExCom with PMO support	Risk reviews will be held during ExCom meetings to have a basis to decide on contingency plans to be executed
Risk communication to the Consortium	Coordinator with PMO support	Communication will be maintained with all partners and proactive participation and visibility of current

		risks will be promoted, using SharePoint
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8 Communication

8.1 Internal communications

The Consortium will adopt the following approaches to ensure efficient communication:

1. Use of **electronic mail** as the main tool for communication within the Consortium.
2. Documentation of discussions, agreements and decisions made by phone is encouraged. Specifically, phone conferences should always have **agenda and minutes**, stored on SharePoint.
3. A **distribution list** will be created which can be used by any Beneficiary depending on the subject of the message. Additional lists may be created as the project evolves, if necessary. The PMO will be responsible for updating the above-mentioned lists with the information received from Beneficiaries.

Distribution list	Description
info@circulardigitalhealth.eu	'generic' email address that could be forwarded to selected people in the consortium

8.1.1 Document repository: SharePoint

A [SharePoint](#) has been created for DiCE to be used as a repository of relevant information and files, which facilitates the exchange of documents within the Consortium (i.e. meeting minutes, documents in progress, final versions and other relevant reports or announcements). The SharePoint platform also provides the possibility to publish meetings and events, work simultaneously in documents and uploading files at Project and WP-level.

All partners, Affiliated Entities and members of DiCE advisory committees are granted access to SharePoint from JPNV. To add any additional responsible person, the PMO should be contacted.

8.1.2 Confidentiality

In accordance with Clause 11.1 and 11.2 of the Consortium Agreement, Beneficiaries need to mark all of their confidential information expressly as "Confidential" prior to circulating it within the consortium. Disclosure of Confidential Information of other Beneficiaries to third parties (subcontractors, external advisors) can only take place to the extent appropriate confidentiality obligations have been put in place in accordance with the Consortium Agreement and only after having received the prior written approval of the Beneficiary concerned.

8.2 External communications

External communications are coordinated by WP1 (WEEE Forum) and described in the Grant Agreement and in the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan. All dissemination

activities will have to go through the dissemination process described in Section 9.2.3 of the Project handbook Deliverable review process.

9 Dissemination

The detailed activities related to the dissemination strategies and responsibilities are included in WP1 of the DoA and in the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan Deliverable review process (Lead: WEEE Forum).

9.1 Rules for dissemination

All communication activities should acknowledge the support of the EU and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages where appropriate):

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text. Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support. When displayed in association with other logos (e.g., of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information. Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer:

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

This statement may be translated into local languages, where appropriate. Translations can be found [HERE](#).

Guidelines and regulation on the use of the EU emblem are available in the website of the EU, [HERE](https://ec.europa.eu/chafea/food/guidelines/documents/eu-emblem-rules_en.pdf) (https://ec.europa.eu/chafea/food/guidelines/documents/eu-emblem-rules_en.pdf).

Some communication formats (e.g., short communications in peer reviewed scientific journals) may not allow the inclusion of logos and web addresses. In these cases, the acknowledgement phrase will suffice.

9.2 Publications Policy

During the Project and for a period of 1 year after the end of the Project, the publication of own Results by one or several Parties, shall be governed by the procedure of Article 17.4 of the Grant Agreement and its Annex 5, Section Dissemination, as well as Clause 9.4.2 of the Consortium Agreement.

9.2.1 Authorship policy

DiCE recommends that authorship be based on the following 4 criteria:

1. Substantial contributions to the conception or design of the work; or the acquisition, analysis, or interpretation of data for the work; and
2. Drafting the work or revising it critically for important intellectual content; and
3. Final approval of the version to be published; and
4. Agreement to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved.

All those designated as authors should meet all four criteria for authorship, and all who meet the four criteria should be identified as authors. These authorship criteria are intended to preserve the status of authorship for those who deserve credit and can take responsibility for the work.

1. Authorship positions and the Corresponding Author will be decided, ideally, before the work is started, by respective Work Package Leads; the ExCom will mediate in case of conflict. All members of the group named as authors should meet all four criteria for authorship, including approval of the final manuscript, and they should be able to take public responsibility for the work and should have full confidence in the accuracy and integrity of the work of other group authors. They will also be expected as individuals to complete conflict-of-interest disclosure forms.

The corresponding author is the one individual who takes primary responsibility for communication with the journal during the manuscript submission, peer review, and publication process, and typically ensures that all the journal's administrative requirements, such as providing details of authorship, ethics committee approval, clinical trial registration documentation, and gathering conflict of interest forms and statements, are properly completed, although these duties may be delegated to one or more co-authors. The corresponding author should be available throughout the submission and peer review process to respond to editorial queries in a timely way and should be available after publication to respond to critiques of the work and cooperate with any requests from the journal for data or additional information should questions about the paper arise after publication.

2. Co-authors must be kept informed. All individuals who meet the first criterion for authorship should have the opportunity to participate in the review, drafting, and final approval of the manuscript. The authorship criteria are not intended for use to disqualify colleagues from authorship who otherwise meet authorship criteria by

denying them the opportunity to meet criterion 2 or 3: drafting the work or revising it critically for important intellectual content; and final approval of the version to be published.

3. All authors will reserve the right to withdraw from authorship at any time. All acknowledgements must be with the consent of the persons involved.
4. A person who has contributed to DiCE but does not meet all four criteria for authorship of the manuscript (see above) should be listed in the acknowledgements section of the same.
5. Free and comprehensive acknowledgement of individuals and groups who have given non-academic support should be done wherever possible (i.e., “*We gratefully acknowledge...*”). For the purposes of DiCE those meriting acknowledgement are defined as/ having provided:
 - materials or methods
 - organisational support
 - clinical cases (but not otherwise involved)
 - technical support
 - Living lab support
 - patients and their relatives
 - funding bodies
 - internal peer review of manuscript or scientific advice
 - participated in writing or technical editing of the manuscript.
6. Individual investigators must not publish or present results without prior submission to the ExCom and must give co-authors appropriate credit.

9.2.2 Reporting scientific publications

WP7 with the support of WP1 and the PMO will provide the DiCE Beneficiaries with a quarterly updated list of the scientific publications produced within the Consortium. Work Package Leads will be requested to inform WP1 lead and the PMO about publication plans for manuscripts related to their respective work packages: draft title, intended authors, target journal, intended submission date. This information will be compiled in a Publication Plan that will be made available in SharePoint.

9.2.3 Review process

The review process prior to Dissemination (Figure 3) applies to all communications, project deliverables, peer-reviewed publications, abstract submissions, etc. including DiCE results and is set out in Clause 9.4.2 of the DiCE Consortium Agreement.

1. Authors send any peer-reviewed publication, conference abstract or poster, communication materials etc., in each case to the extent including Results of the project, to the DiCE PMO to initiate the review process, at least 60 days prior to the publication deadline.
2. The PMO checks for the correct use of the authorship and EU funding acknowledgements, disclaimer, logos and DiCE website.

3. The PMO forwards the materials to the Beneficiaries for review in accordance with Clause 9.4.2 of the Consortium Agreement.
4. The Beneficiaries have 30 days to provide review comments. The PMO provides all feedback to the Author(s) of the material(s). The remaining 30 days till publication will be reserved for addressing the comments by the Authors.
5. If necessary, the Author(s) adjusts the material.
 - a. For publications: the Author submits the publication. Once the submitted material is accepted for publication, the Author(s) will provide the final version to PMO
 - b. For project Deliverables: the PMO submits to the EU Portal
6. The PMO finalizes the information in the dissemination tracker & upload the material(s) to SharePoint and to the EU Portal.

Figure 3. Schematic overview of the review process.

9.2.4 Open Access

Each Partner must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results, must manage the digital research data generated in the action ('data') responsibly, in line with the FAIR principles. Where the call conditions impose additional obligations regarding open science practices, the beneficiaries must also comply with those.

In accordance with Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement, obligations include:

1. At the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, is deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications.
2. Immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g., CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND) and
3. Information is given via the repository about any research output, or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.

Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements.

10 Intellectual Property Rights

For provisions regarding Intellectual Property Rights, including but not limited to Background, Results, and Access Rights, please refer to Article 16 of the Grant Agreement and Sections 9 and 10 of the Consortium Agreement.

11 Gender issues

Gender dimensions are relevant in the context of the project as described in section 1.2.5 of the Grant Agreement. The use of living labs in WP4 allows to test for these potential gender, societal and cultural differences at a very early stage following the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) principles. Gender stereotypes will be avoided in descriptions and in our activities. Gender neutral language will be used when developing communication materials or campaigns.

Section 1.2.4 of the DoA Part B contains how the RRI process aided during the setup of the project to achieve gender balanced teams. Gender mainstreaming is also described in Annex 5, article 14 of the Grant Agreement and gender equality is monitored during DiCE through the gender balance of the teams. Beneficiaries must aim, to the extent possible, for a gender balance at all levels of personnel assigned to the action, including at supervisory and managerial level.

ANNEX I: Internal progress report template

DiCE Internal Progress Report Template (6-months)

GENERAL INFORMATION

Participant Acronym:	
Date of the report:	
Contact person:	

FINANCIALS

Total effort spent in the period (pm)(*):	
Total cost in EUR (approx.)(**):	
<p>(*): Optionally, you can indicate effort expressed in Full-Time Equivalents (FTEs), please specify so.</p> <p>(**) Please provide also details on “major costs” (>10,000 Eur) within the period, including the type of expenses (travels, subcontracting, etc).</p>	

WORK PROGRESS

Main achievements and results
<p><i>See below the following example:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Developed v1.2 of prototype X</i> - <i>Elaborated second draft of guidelines for XXX</i> - <i>Etc.</i>
Meetings attended (optional)
Deliverables/Documents reviewed (optional)

ANNEX II: DiCE Risk documentation form

DiCE Risk Documentation Form (RDF)

Risk ID*: Click or tap here to enter text.

Resolved **Active** **Inactive**

Risk Title:			
Classification:			
WP/Tasks:			
Detection date:	Click or tap to enter a date.	Update:	Click or tap to enter a date.
Risk reporter:		Version:	
Risk Owner**:			
Risk Source:			
Risk description:			
Consequence:			
Mitigation:			
Other comments			

* Risk ID codes are completed by PMO

** The Risk Owner is the partner in the best position to recommend mitigation strategies, develop contingency plans and monitor the status of the risk.